

Treatment of Cutting Oily-Wastewater by Sono-Fenton Process: Experimental Approach and Combined Process

Authors : Pisut Painmanakul, Thawatchai Chintateerachai, Supanid Lertlapwasin, Nusara Rojvilavan, Tanun Chalermssinsuwan, Nattawin Chawaloessphonsiya, Onanong Larpparisudthi

Abstract : Conventional coagulation, advance oxidation process (AOPs), and the combined process were evaluated and compared for its suitability to treat the stabilized cutting-oil wastewater. The 90% efficiency was obtained from the coagulation at $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ dosage of 150 mg/L and pH 7. On the other hands, efficiencies of AOPs for 30 minutes oxidation time were 10% for acoustic oxidation, 12% for acoustic oxidation with hydrogen peroxide, 76% for Fenton, and 92% sono-Fenton processes. The highest efficiency for effective oil removal of AOPs required large amount of chemical. Therefore, AOPs were studied as a post-treatment after conventional separation process. The efficiency was considerable as the effluent COD can pass the standard required for industrial wastewater discharge with less chemical and energy consumption.

Keywords : cutting oily-wastewater, advance oxidation process, sono-fenton, combined process

Conference Title : ICEBESE 2014 : International Conference on Environmental, Biological, Ecological Sciences and Engineering

Conference Location : Paris, France

Conference Dates : December 30-31, 2014